

INTERLAMINAR FRACTURE OF CF/EP COMPOSITE CONTAINING A DUAL-COMPONENT MICROENCAPSULATED SELF-HEALANT

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents an experimental study on self-healing ability of carbon fibre/epoxy (CF/EP) composite laminates with microencapsulated epoxy and its hardener (mercaptan) as healing agent. Both epoxy- and hardener-loaded microcapsules (large with average size of 120 μm and small with 65 μm) prepared by in situ polymerization in an oil-in-water emulsion and they were dry-dispersed with ratio 1:1 on the surface of unidirectional carbon fabric layer. The laminates were fabricated using vacuum assisted resin infusion (VARI) process. Width tapered double cantilever beam (WTDCB) specimens were used to measure mode-I interlaminar fracture toughness of CF/EP composites with a pre-crack at the centre plane where the microcapsules were placed. It was found that the incorporation of dual component healant stored in fragile microcapsules can provide the laminates with delamination damage on healing capability by recovering as high as 80% or its original fracture toughness. It was also found that, the recovery of fracture toughness is directly influenced by the amount of healant covering the fracture plane, with the highest healing efficiency obtained for the laminate with large capsules.

1 INTRODUCTION

The concept of self-healing of materials with encapsulated healing agents composed of both healing resin and curing catalyst was proposed more than half a century ago. However, it did not evolve into a viable method because of a very limited “no-curing” lifetime, until recently when researchers developed techniques to encapsulate or graft the healing resin and curing catalyst independently. In the early 2000s researchers from University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign USA developed a self-healing material system consisting microencapsulated healing agent (dicyclopentadiene (DCPD)) and a catalytic chemical trigger within an epoxy matrix to automatically heal cracks, which can be seen as an engineering solution to address materials failure [1]. This self-healing ability helps the materials to recover their load bearing ability after damage happen, with some approaching 90% [2-6].

Various approaches of self-healing mechanism have been established over the years. The three approaches receiving most attention are the capsule based healing system [1-7], intrinsic healing system [8-10] and hollow fibre embedment [11]. Among these systems, microcapsules based self-healing has advantages to be applied in polymer composites compared to the other two systems; this includes the ease of dispersion into matrix resins [12].

Figure 1 shows the basic concept of a microcapsule-based self-healing system with dual component healing agent. In this system, two-component healant consists of polymerizable monomers and its hardener were encapsulated separately in fragile capsules and incorporated into a matrix material [6].

These capsules rupture and release the monomer and hardener upon approaching of a crack, the mix of monomer and hardener polymerizes and subsequently heals the crack [13].

Figure 1: Schematic of crack/delamination closure of fibre composites self-healing mechanism

Most of studies in self-healing materials were focused on neat resins systems instead of structural composites. Disturbance on fibre orientation by microcapsules and difficulty to uniformly disperse the microcapsules to provide consistent healing throughout the structure can be a challenge in adapting the microcapsule-based self-healing technique to structural composites [13]. Kessler et al., [14] have successfully demonstrated maximum 80% recovery of interlaminar fracture toughness of CF/EP fabricated using wet hand lay-up and compression moulding using an epoxy resin mixed with capsules. This healing efficiency was achieved by using the microencapsulated DCPD resin and Grubb's catalyst at the interply region to initiates a ring-opening-metathesis-polymerization (ROMP) of DCPD while healing at 80°C. A study by Yin et al., [15, 16] implemented microencapsulated epoxy and latent curing agent as two-component healant in a woven glass fibre composite with a fibre volume fraction of 27%. It was observed that over 70% recovery of original interlaminar fracture toughness can be achieved with 30 wt% microencapsulated epoxy and 2 wt% microencapsulated latent hardener in the matrix.

Self-sealing functionality of a woven glass fibre composite by addition of encapsulated DCPD and Grubb's catalyst as healant in matrix was demonstrated by Moll et al. [17]. It was found that after being damaged by repeated indentation at prescribed loads, self-sealing was observed in composites laminates with no nitrogen flow through the thickness direction of the composite.

A dual-component self-healing system consisting microencapsulated epoxy and mercaptan as hardener, has been reported [6, 18], with 104% maximum healing efficiency of neat epoxy. Lee et al., [19], and Yuan et al., [20] have reported compressive behaviour after impact damage in glass fibre reinforced epoxy laminates incorporated with this healing system. Both studies show the dual-component healing system enables self-repair of glass fibre reinforced epoxy laminates at a certain degree.

In this study, we developed a dual-component healing system for fabricating CF/EP composites from carbon fibre uni-fabrics with vacuum assisted resin-infusion. The objective is to further understand the self-healing capacity of structural composites with such a healing system, and it is expected that the findings will help practical applications of such materials.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1. Microencapsulation of a dual-component self-healant

For the dual-component self-healant used in this study, a diglycidyl-ether of bisphenol-A epoxy resin – Araldite-F (Ciba-Geigy, Australia) was employed as the polymerizable component of the healing agent. Pentaerythritol tetrakis (3-mercaptopropionate) (PETMP) (Sigma Aldrich, Australia) was used as a hardener for the epoxy and 2,4,6-Tris (dimethylaminomethyl) phenol (DMP-30). This catalyst was infused into hardener loaded microcapsules as an accelerator and for better thermal properties. Both epoxy and its hardener were encapsulated independently in melamine-formaldehyde according to the procedures described elsewhere [6, 18].

To study the effect of microcapsule size and distribution on healing ability of CF/EP composites, microcapsules with different mean sizes were prepared. The shell thickness of the microcapsules is about 1.50 ± 0.30 micron as observed with SEM (scanning electron microscopy). The core content of the epoxy-loaded microcapsules (weight ratio of core to microcapsule shell) is about 96.70 wt % and 93.10 wt% for hardener-loaded ones as determined by the Soxhlet extraction method. For Type A capsules the average size is 110.6 μm for epoxy-loaded microcapsules (Figure 2a) and 136.4 μm for hardener-loaded microcapsules (Figure 2b), meanwhile for Type B capsules, the average size is about 65.2 μm for epoxy-loaded microcapsules (Figure 2c) and 66.1 μm for hardener-loaded microcapsules (Figure 2d).

Figure 2: SEM micrograph of microcapsules (a) Type A epoxy-loaded microcapsules (b) rough surface of Type A hardener-loaded microcapsules (c) Type B epoxy-loaded microcapsules (d) collapse phenomenon of Type B hardener loaded microcapsules

Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) was used to investigate the reactivity of the prepared capsules. Small amounts of cracked capsules (10-20 mg) at a weight ratio of 1:1 between the epoxy and hardener were heated from 20 to 200°C at a rate of 10°C/min in an environment with N₂. Figure 3 shows the exothermal reaction curve of the mixture. The exothermic reaction peaks at 102.62°C with the onset temperature at 83.49°C is the curing temperatures of the mixture. These results indicate healing in a

material with the capsules of epoxy and hardener will occur in a temperature range of 70 to 100°C when the epoxy and hardener are released from the capsules.

Figure 3: Exothermic reaction curve of epoxy and hardener mixture

2.2. CF/EP laminates with self-healant

T300 unidirectional carbon fibre fabric (FGI Fibre Glass International, Australia) and a diglycidyl ether of bisphenol A (DGEBA) epoxy resin (Araldite-F, Ciba-Geigy, Australia), were used to fabricate CF/EP composites in this study, with Piperidine (Sigma—Aldrich, Australia) as curing agent. Composite panels were manufactured using a vacuum-assisted resin infusion (VARI) process. Sixteen pieces of 300 mm × 250 mm sheets were cut from T300 unidirectional carbon fabric and stacked together. At one end of the laminate, a very thin polyimide film was embedded at the central plane, coated with a release agent, to form a starter crack for mode-I interlaminar fracture toughness test. For the CF/EP laminates with encapsulated healant, microcapsules of the epoxy and hardener, Type A or Type B, were mixed at a weight ratio of 1:1 loaded and then were dry-dispersed using a particle sifter onto the top surface of carbon fibre fabric, modulated by the mass of capsules per unit area. Only three interlayer regions (the central, immediately above and below the central) of laminates were incorporated with these microcapsules (Figure 4).

Figure 4: Distribution of epoxy and hardener loaded microcapsules on top of carbon fibre fabric

A temperature of 60 °C in the sealed vacuum bag was maintained during VARI. The vacuum bag with the resin-infiltrated carbon fibre fabric stack was then moved onto a hot press at a pressure of 0.4 MPa to achieve a composite laminate with a high fibre volume fraction of about 65% and to ensure the flatness of the cured laminate panel.

Three types of laminates were fabricated, as listed in Table 1. Base CF/EP laminate was fabricated to serve as the benchmark without microcapsules. Type A CF/EP laminates were fabricated with Type A microcapsules (75 g/m²) while Type B CF/EP laminates were fabricated with Type B microcapsules (75 g/m²). The laminates were cured in the hot press at 120 °C for 16 h. The cured composite panels were then cut into specimens using water jet cutting.

Specimen type	No of WTDCB test	Details	Healant concentration (g/m ²)		Healing Conditions
			Epoxy loaded	Hardener loaded	
Base CF/EP	5	Epoxy matrix with CF (Fracture surfaces reattached with mercaptan hardened epoxy adhesive)	37.5	37.5	70°C, 24 hrs.
Type A CF/EP	5	Epoxy matrix with epoxy/hardener microcapsules embedded on the surface of CF	37.5	37.5	70°C, 24 hrs.
Type B CF/EP	5	Epoxy matrix with epoxy/hardener microcapsules embedded on the surface of CF	37.5	37.5	70°C, 24 hrs.

Table 1: Summary and details of the various laminates

Mode-I interlaminar fracture toughness of CF/EP laminates with and without the encapsulated healant were studied by adapting a width tapered double cantilever beam (WTDCB) specimens [14] (Figure 5). A WTDCB specimen is designed for constant compliance with crack length, so that the interlaminar fracture toughness, G_{IC} is independent of crack length [21].

$$G_{IC} = \frac{12P_c^2 K^2}{E_1 h^3} \quad (1)$$

where P_c is the applied load, E_1 is the modulus of elasticity in the longitudinal direction, h is the specimen half thickness. K is a constant aspect ratio of on WTDCB ($K = a/b(a)$) [14], where $b(a)$ is the width of specimen at crack length a , Figure 5.

Figure 5: Geometry of WTDCB specimen for mode-I interlaminar fracture of CF/EP laminates

2.3. Mode-I interlaminar fracture

Mode-I interlaminar fracture toughness test was conducted on an Instron 5567 universal testing machine equipped with 1 kN load cell at a displacement rate of 5 mm/min. The WTDCB specimen was loaded until the crack reaches the non-tapered region of the specimen (i.e. crack propagated from $a = 60$ mm to approximately $a = 100$ mm) and then unloaded. The load and displacement were recorded throughout the test. At least 5 specimens were tested for each type of CF/EP laminates.

For the base CF/EP specimens, after the crack propagated to about $a=100$ mm (the end of tapered region), the specimens were quickly unloaded and injected with the epoxy monomer mixed with mercaptan and DMP-30 as catalyst (i.e. mercaptan hardened epoxy adhesive), which is the same as that released from the capsules. The fractured specimen was then clamped using steel plates and then placed in an oven at 70°C for 24 hours. After healing, the specimens were cooled down to room temperature and tested again following the same mode-I interlaminar fracture procedure. Healing of these specimens serves as a benchmark on how strong this dual-component (epoxy/mercaptan) healant can get when the full coverage of healant on fracture surfaces is achieved.

For self-healing CF/EP specimens, after quickly unloaded, the specimen was clamped using steel plates to bring the two crack surfaces together and then placed in an oven at 70°C for 24 hours. The healed specimens were tested again following the same procedure. The morphology of fracture surfaces was then examined using Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM).

2.4. Quantification of healing efficiency (η)

Some parameters have been adopted to describe the healing performance of polymers [22]. Healing of CF/EP in this study was quantified by the recovery of its fracture toughness [14, 16]. Therefore, healing efficiency can be defined by the ratio of fracture toughness of the healed specimen, $G_{\text{IC}(\text{healed})}$, and that of original specimen $G_{\text{IC}(\text{original})}$ [22],

$$\eta (\%) = \sqrt{\frac{G_{\text{IC}(\text{healed})}}{G_{\text{IC}(\text{original})}}} \times 100 \quad (2)$$

Instead of stable crack propagation, unstable or “stick-slip” crack propagation was observed for interlaminar fracture of the CF/EP laminates, which produces multiple peaks of critical load, P_c , for onset of crack propagation, leading to multiple values of the interlaminar fracture toughness, G_{IC} [14, 23, 24]. Due to this, instead of characterizing the healing efficiency with only the maximum value of fracture toughness, $G_{\text{IC}}^{\text{max}}$, the average value of fracture toughness, $G_{\text{IC}}^{\text{average}}$, gathered from multiple peaks, P_c , was also taken into consideration. Average healing efficiency, η_{average} is defined as a ratio of the average fracture toughness in healed specimens ($G_{\text{IC}(\text{healed})}^{\text{average}}$) to the average fracture toughness in original specimens ($G_{\text{IC}(\text{original})}^{\text{average}}$),

$$\eta_{\text{average}} (\%) = \sqrt{\frac{G_{\text{IC}(\text{healed})}^{\text{average}}}{G_{\text{IC}(\text{original})}^{\text{average}}}} \times 100 \quad (3)$$

The maximum healing efficiency, η_{max} , is defined as the ratio of the maximum fracture toughness in healed specimens ($G_{\text{IC}(\text{healed})}^{\text{max}}$) to the average fracture toughness in original specimens ($G_{\text{IC}(\text{original})}^{\text{average}}$),

$$\eta_{\text{max}} (\%) = \sqrt{\frac{G_{\text{IC}(\text{healed})}^{\text{max}}}{G_{\text{IC}(\text{original})}^{\text{average}}}} \times 100 \quad (4)$$

2.5. Relationship between healant covered surface area and healing efficiency

It was observed that the healant coverage on the fracture surfaces is related to the healing efficiency in CF/EP laminates. Quantitative assessment of the area covered by healant was conducted using ImageJ open-source image analyser. Images of fracture surfaces were obtained using SEM. The healant surface area was measured with the assumption that the fracture surface of healant is flatter than that of CF/EP composites. 20 images were randomly taken on the fracture surface from each Type A self-healing CF/EP specimens, with 5 images from the crack initiation area. Bonded surface area (BSA) is then quantified as the ratio of the average healant covered surface area (HSA) to the total scanned area of fracture surface (TSA),

$$\text{Bonded Surface Area(\%)} = \frac{\text{HSA}_{\text{average}}}{\text{TSA}} \times 100 \quad (5)$$

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Mode-I fracture toughness evaluation

Figure 8a shows typical load-displacement curves of interlaminar fracture of CF/EP laminates with Type A or Type B capsules in comparison to that of the base CF/EP laminate. In all cases the load increased linearly until the onset of delamination; then the crack propagated in stick-slip mode. The values of averaged fracture toughness were calculated using Equation (1). In Figure 8b, G_{IC}^{average} for the base CF/EP laminates were reduced after adding the capsules. G_{IC}^{average} of the base CF/EP laminates is 539.4 J/m², whereas G_{IC}^{average} of Type A and Type B CF/EP are 514.4 J/m² and 335.2 J/m², respectively. The microcapsules in the interlaminar regions apparently act as imperfection - voids (Figure 8a), thus directly influencing G_{IC} of composites [25]. The size of microcapsules also has a direct influence on the fracture toughness of CF/EP. It can be seen in Figure 8b that the interlaminar fracture toughness is lowest for the CF/EP laminate with small microcapsules (Type B). Figure 2d shows the collapsed Type B hardener-loaded microcapsules, which indicates that the capsules are flexible and may not retain the spherical shape during contact. This can promote agglomeration of capsules with poor adhesion between them. When delamination happens, instead of crack propagating through the capsule, the crack path manoeuvres around the capsules (Figure 8b). Large clusters of capsules may also leave voids between them, Figure 8c, which contributes to low fracture resistance.

Figure 7: Interlaminar fracture of base laminate and laminates with Type A and Type B microcapsules; (a) typical load-displacement curves and (b) G_{IC}^{average} for the base and self-healing laminates

Figure 8: Fracture surfaces of CF/EP laminates; (a) voids, (b) dimples from debonded microcapsules and (c) clustering of smaller size microcapsules

3.2. CF/EP injected with healant

Figure 9 show the typical load-displacement curves for the base CF/EP laminate and that healed with the injected healant. The crack propagation onset occurs at a much higher load for CF/EP laminate healed by injecting healant between the fracture surfaces, and the delamination onset load after healing is clearly higher than that for the original fracture. As the crack advances, the load increased in a stable manner until it reached its maximum load and dropped towards the end of tapered region of the specimen. This may be associated with additional fracture mechanisms, such as fibre bridging and side cracking, which were not present during the original fracture. However, the result indicates that this dual-mechanism (epoxy/mercaptan) healant can potentially heal CF/EP laminates with more than 100% recovery of its fracture toughness.

Figure 9: Typical load-displacement curves of interlaminar fracture of original fracture and fracture after healing of base CF/EP laminates with injected healant

3.3. Self-healing efficiency of CF/EP

For the typical load-displacement curves of CF/EP laminates with capsules in Figure 10, both original and healed laminates show stick-slip fracture behaviour, but with some clear differences. For fracture of the original laminates, after onset of delamination, the loads at “peak” and “valley” seem to remain between the lower and upper bounds as the crack propagated. For the laminate with Type A capsules, the load in all healed laminates increase with the crack growth, Figure 10a. As the main crack advances, microcapsules breaks releasing healant that has the ability to flow towards the narrower space between the upper and lower fracture surfaces through capillary motion, transferring more healant towards the main

crack tip [1]. This explains the ascending curve of the load with crack growth, as the better healed crack region developed in the region towards the crack tip produces high crack growth resistance, as demonstrated by the enhanced fracture resistance in the healed base laminate with injected healant in Figure 9. The average healing efficiency, η_{avg} , and maximum healing efficiency, η_{max} , for CF/EP laminates with Type A capsules are 69% and 80% respectively. The values of both η_{avg} and η_{max} are comparable to those reported before for a CF/EP laminate [14]. The fracture of healed CF/EP laminates with Type B capsules shows unstable crack propagation with clearly low values of peak load, P_c . The CF/EP laminates with Type B capsules showed the values of 54% and 57% for the average healing efficiency, η_{avg} , and the maximum healing efficiency, η_{max} , which are much lower than those for the laminates with Type A capsules. Table 2 summarizes the results of mode-I interlaminar fracture tests and healing efficiency of the CF/EP laminates. As discussed in the previous section, small Type B capsules promote agglomeration of capsules with poor adhesion between them, and the crack path manoeuvres around the capsules without breaking them. The large clusters of small capsules means smaller areas of fracture surfaces can be covered by the healant released from the capsules, leading to poor healing ability.

Figure 10: Interlaminar fracture of original CF/EP laminates and those after healing

Sample Type	$G_{IC}^{average}$ (virgin) (J/m ²)	$G_{IC}^{average}$ (healed) (J/m ²)	G_{IC}^{max} (healed) (J/m ²)	$\eta_{average}$ (%)	η_{max} (%)
Base CF/EP*	539.38	769.28	934.33	116	126
Type-A	514.55	253.47	337.65	69	80
Type-B	335.06	139.58	146.67	54	56

*For the base CF/EP, the healing was achieved using direct injection of dual-component healant in the delaminated area.

Table 2: Mode-I interlaminar fracture toughness and healing efficiency of base CF/EP and CF/EP laminates with Type A and Type B capsules

3.4. Relationship between healant covered surface area and healing efficiency

Figure 11 shows the relationship between the healant rich area on fracture surface and the healing efficiency for the CF/EP laminate with Type A capsules. It can be seen that the healing efficiency is clearly dependent upon the bonded surface area by healing agent. To achieve a high value of healing

efficiency, wide-spreading of healant on fracture surface is certainly needed, as demonstrated in the base laminate with the injected healant. However, there is a clear difference between the healant rich areas from one specimen to another. This is strongly related to distribution of microcapsules in matrix materials, which is related to dispersion of microcapsules on top of carbon fabrics before resin infusion. In addition, resin transfer during the VARI process may also promote non-uniform distribution of microcapsules, such as washing and agglomeration.

Figure 11: Relationship between healant-area on fracture surface and healing efficiency of CF/EP laminate with Type A microcapsules

3.5. Fractographic Analysis

Figure 12 shows SEM fractographs of fracture surface of CF/EP laminates with Type A and Type B capsules. For Type A, it can be seen that fracture surface was roughly 50% covered by the healant. As previously discussed, large size microcapsules store more healant in them, subsequently resulting bigger healant rich areas. However, small capsules of Type B intend to form clusters. This directly influences the healant rich area; apart from that, smaller microcapsules contain a small amount of healant. With the smaller amount of healant, patchy healing happens on the surface causing insufficient coverage on the fracture surface area.

(a) Type A

(b) Type B

Figure 12: SEM fractographs of CF/EP laminates with microencapsulated healant (a) Type A with healant covering fracture surface (b) patchy healing on Type-B fracture surface

4 CONCLUSIONS

A two-component healing system consisting of encapsulated epoxy and mercaptan as its hardener was developed for producing self-healing CF/EP laminates with a high fibre volume fraction of 65%,

fabricated using a VARI process. The interlaminar fracture of CF/EP laminates with large and small capsules was characterised using WTDCB specimens, and the self-healing efficiency of CF/EP laminates on interlaminar fracture was evaluated addressing the effect of size of capsules. Base on the results, a few useful points can be drawn:

1. Incorporation of dual-component healant stored in fragile microcapsules can provide CF/EP laminates with self-healing capability by recovering as high as 80% of its original fracture toughness.
2. Distribution and size of microcapsules have effects on the original interlaminar fracture toughness of CF/EP laminates. Both large and small capsules reduce the original interlaminar fracture toughness. Smaller capsules intend to agglomerate, causing poor adhesion between the microcapsules and leading more reduction in the fracture toughness.
3. Distribution and size of microcapsules also has an effect on the interlaminar fracture toughness of CF/EP laminates after healing. Larger capsules provide high healing efficiency for CF/EP laminates, with more healant stored and released to cover the fracture surfaces; small capsules provide low healing efficiency for CF/EP laminates with more clustered capsules. The healing efficiency is clearly dependent on the coverage of healant on fracture surfaces; wider coverage results in higher healing efficiency.

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REFERENCES

- [1] S. R. White, N. R. Sottos, P. H. Geubelle, J. S. Moore, M. R. Kessler, S. R. Sriram, E. N. Brown, and S. Viswanathan, Autonomic healing of polymer composites, *Nature* **409** (2001), pp. 794-797
- [2] E.N. Brown, N.R. Sottos, S.R. White, Fracture testing of a self-healing polymer composite, *Experimental Mechanics*, **42** (2002), pp. 372-379.
- [3] H. Jin, C.L. Mangun, A.S. Griffin, J.S. Moore, N.R. Sottos, S.R. White, Thermally Stable Autonomic Healing in Epoxy using a Dual-Microcapsule System, *Advanced Materials*, **26** (2014), pp. 282-287.
- [4] L. Yao, Y.C. Yuan, M.Z. Rong, M.Q. Zhang, Self-healing linear polymers based on RAFT polymerization, *Polymer*, **52** (2011), pp. 3137-3145
- [5] T. Yin, M.Z. Rong, M.Q. Zhang, G.C. Yang, Self-healing epoxy composites – Preparation and effect of the healant consisting of microencapsulated epoxy and latent curing agent, *Composites Science and Technology*, **67** (2007), pp. 201-212
- [6] Y.C. Yuan, M.Z. Rong, M.Q. Zhang, J. Chen, G.C. Yang, X.M. Li, Self-Healing Polymeric Materials Using Epoxy/Mercaptan as the Healant, *Macromolecules*, **41** (2008), pp. 5197-5202
- [7] D.S. Xiao, Y.C. Yuan, M.Z. Rong, M.Q. Zhang, Self-healing epoxy based on cationic chain polymerization, *Polymer*, **50** (2009), pp. 2967-2975
- [8] S. Hayes, F. Jones, K. Marshiya, W. Zhang, A self-healing thermosetting composite material, *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, **38** (2007), pp. 1116-1120
- [9] X. Luo, R. Ou, D.E. Eberly, A. Singhal, W. Viratayaporn, P.T. Mather, A Thermoplastic/Thermoset Blend Exhibiting Thermal Mending and Reversible Adhesion, *ACS applied materials & interfaces*, **1** (2009), pp. 612-620
- [10] M.A.M. Rahmathullah, G.R. Palmese, Crack-healing behavior of epoxy–amine thermosets, *Journal of applied polymer science*, **113** (2009), pp. 2191-2201

- [11] R. Trask, G. Williams, I. Bond, Bioinspired self-healing of advanced composite structures using hollow glass fibres, *Journal of the royal society Interface*, **4** (2007), pp. 363-371
- [12] X. Liu, H. Zhang, J. Wang, Z. Wang, S. Wang, Preparation of epoxy microcapsule based self-healing coatings and their behavior, *Surface and Coatings Technology*, **206** (2012), pp. 4976-4980
- [13] I.P. Bond, R.S. Trask, H.R. Williams, Self-Healing Fiber-Reinforced Polymer Composites, *MRS Bulletin*, **33** (2008), pp. 770-774
- [14] M.R. Kessler, N.R. Sottos, S.R. White, Self-healing structural composite materials, *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, **34** (2003), pp. 743-753
- [15] T. Yin, M.Z. Rong, M.Q. Zhang, J.Q. Zhao, Durability of self-healing woven glass fabric/epoxy composites, *Smart Materials and Structures*, **18** (2009), pp. 074001
- [16] T. Yin, L. Zhou, M.Z. Rong, M.Q. Zhang, Self-healing woven glass fabric/epoxy composites with the healant consisting of micro-encapsulated epoxy and latent curing agent, *Smart Materials and Structures*, **17** (2008), pp. 015019
- [17] J. J.L. Moll, S.R. White, N.R. Sottos, A Self-sealing Fiber-reinforced Composite, *Journal of Composite Materials*, **44** (2010), pp. 2573-2585
- [18] Y.C. Yuan, M.Z. Rong, M.Q. Zhang, G.C. Yang, Study of factors related to performance improvement of self-healing epoxy based on dual encapsulated healant, *Polymer*, **50** (2009), pp. 5771-5781
- [19] J. Lee, D. Bhattacharyya, M.Q. Zhang, Y.W. Mai, Y.C. Yuan, Compression Behavior of a Self-Healing Fibre Reinforced Epoxy Composite, *Applied Mechanics and Materials*, **55** (2011) 1281-1286
- [20] Y.C. Yuan, Y. Ye, M.Z. Rong, H. Chen, J. Wu, M.Q. Zhang, S.X. Qin, G.C. Yang, Self-healing of low-velocity impact damage in glass fabric/epoxy composites using an epoxy-mercaptan healing agent, *Smart Materials and Structures*, **20** (2011), pp. 015024.
- [21] G. Yaniv, I.M. Daniel, Height-tapered double cantilever beam specimen for study of rate effects on fracture toughness of composites, *ASTM STP*, **972** (1988), pp. 241-258.
- [22] R. Wool, K. O'connor, A theory crack healing in polymers, *Journal of Applied Physics*, **52** (1981), pp. 5953-5963.
- [23] A. Kinloch, J. Williams, Crack blunting mechanisms in polymers, *Journal of Materials Science*, **15** (1980), pp. 987-996.
- [24] A. Smiley, R. Pipes, Rate Effects on Mode I Interlaminar Fracture Toughness in Composite Materials, *Journal of composite materials*, **21** (1987), pp. 670-687.
- [25] H. Yoshida, T. Ogasa, R. Hayashi, Statistical approach to the relationship between ILSS and void content of CFRP, *Composites Science and Technology*, **25** (1986), pp. 3-18